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**DEDUPLICATION OF DATA IN TEXT FILES IN
CLOUD STORAGE**

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ABSTRACT

The world around us consists of so much information which has to be interpreted. When this interpretation takes place we obtain something called data. Data about this interpreted data is called Metadata. For example, File consists of Information so we can say File is data and details like File name, file size etc. are Metadata. Data is stored in storage spaces. Currently the most dominantly used storage method is Cloud Storage. One of the major issues faced by Cloud storage is data redundancy. To solve this issue one should achieve Data Deduplication. Data Deduplication is a concept where unique data or a particular pattern of data is identified and stored. This is then compared to other data available in the system. If a match is found, then the data is replaced by a link or a reference to the stored data. The proposed system aims at building a data deduplication mechanism which provides a practical solution that is more secure than previous techniques in some cases.

Introduction:

Cloud computing is a platform that provides seemingly unlimited “virtualized “resources to users across the whole Internet, while hiding platform and implementation details. Highly available storage and massively parallel computing resources are provided at relatively low costs. Prevalent use of cloud, an increasing amount of data is being stored and shared by users with specified privileges, which define the access rights of the data stored. In short we can say that cloud computing is computing as a business model that provide computing resources as a service on demand to customers over the Internet. [3]

Cloud can be used in multiple forms. For instance: customers can use cloud storage as a backup to store a backup copy of data, as opposed to maintaining their own storage disks. Establishments have moved their archival storage to the cloud which they can achieve more capacity at a lesser cost, rather than buying additional physical storage. Applications running in the cloud also require temporary or permanent data storage in order to support the applications.

As the amount of data in the cloud is rapidly increasing, customers expect to reach the on-demand cloud services at any time, while providers are required to maintain system availability and process a large amount of data. Providers need a way to dramatically reduce data volumes, so they can reduce costs while saving energy consumption for running large storage systems. [2] This is where the concept of data deduplication can play a key role.

In this paper we propose a novel approach that makes use of data deduplication. Logical pointers are created for other copies instead of storing redundant data. Deduplication can reduce both storage space and network bandwidth [5].

Literature Survey

The following are the existing mechanisms of architecture available for deduplication for cloud backup services such as SAM [11], AA-Dedupe [8], CABdedupe [9], and SHHC [10]. SAM [10] system architecture is composed of three subsystems: File Agent, Master Server and Storage Server. Clients subscribe to backup services, then File Agents are distributed and installed on their machines, while service provider provides Master Server and Storage Server in datacentre to serve the backup requests from clients. Most of existing solutions that use deduplication technology primarily focus on the reduction of backup time while ignoring the restoration time. The authors proposed CABdedupe [16], a performance booster for both cloud backup and cloud restore operations, which is a middleware that is orthogonal and can be integrated into any existing backup system. CABdedupe consists of CAB-Client and CAB-Server, which is placed on the original client and server modules in existing backup systems.

The main aim of these related works are the following: SAM aims to achieve an optimal trade-off between deduplication efficiency and deduplication overhead, CABdedupe reduces both backup time and restoration time. AA-Dedupe [15] aims to reduce the computational overhead, increase throughput and transfer efficiency, while SHHC [17] tries to improve fingerprint storage and lookup mechanism, however has a concern of scalability. SHHC is a novel Scalable Hybrid Hash Cluster designed for improving response times to fingerprint lookup process. Because of a large number of simultaneous requests are expected in cloud backup services.

In order to solve this problem, the hash cluster is designed for high load-balancing, scalability and minimizing the cost for each fingerprint lookup query. The hash cluster is designed as middleware between the clients and the cloud storage. It provides the fingerprint storage and lookup service.

There are other works on deduplication storages which their architectures are designed for scalability issue, for example; Extreme Binning [12], and Droplet [13].

Extreme Binning is used to build a distributed file backup system. The architecture of such system is composed of several backup nodes. Each backup node consists of a compute core

and RAM along with a dedicated attached disk. The first task when a file arrives to the system for backup is, it must be chunked. The system can delegate this task to any one of the backup nodes by choosing one according to the system load at that time. After chunking, stateless routing algorithm is used to route the chunked file by using its chunk ID. The chunked file will be routed to a backup node where it will be deduplicated and stored.

MODEL AND ARCHITECTURE

A. Proposed System

The system can upload non secure documents be in text or doc files into the cloud. This removes redundancy. The process also eliminates extra usage of storage space and unnecessary usage of bandwidth by eradicating uploading of redundant data.

B. System Architecture

The architectural design will show the conceptual model of the application. It shows the overall architecture of the system.

The system has an admin who is the owner of the system. The admin controls the system. The user has to register with the system. The user logs in and uploads or downloads into the system. As per the option chosen, the alert is sent by the system using pop up messages.

C. Implementation of the system

The resulting system is expected to perform the following tasks i.e. inserting the data, updating the data and deleting the data. Hashing techniques are used to extract the metadata. This data will be then compared with previously existing values of the data already existing in the system. If there is a match we can conclude that redundant data exists and thereby eliminate it.

Advantages:

- Obviously storage space can be saved.
- Because redundant files will not be uploaded but only a reference will be given to the existing file, the energy consumed to store it and the bandwidth used for uploading also can be saved.
- Overall maintenance becomes easier, and also overall costs can also be reduced.

CONCLUSION

In this work we present a method which is a data deduplication mechanism which provides a practical solution that is more secure than previous techniques in some cases.

The storage space will be saved; the energy consumed to store and maintain the data is reduced since redundancy is reduced. Also the bandwidth will be saved. The maintenance becomes smooth, thereby reducing overall cost.

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